

Assembling the Strategies for Learning Vocabulary

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Some useful conventional learning vocabulary strategies for learners are presented. The aim is to develop the learners in learning vocabulary in terms of useful strategies because learning grammar along with vocabulary enables them to use the language for communication.

Literature Review

Vital role of learning vocabulary

It is further described that vocabulary knowledge is related to language use: vocabulary knowledge enables language use and, in turn, language use induces increasing vocabulary knowledge. (Nation, 2001) Most learners acquire sufficient vocabulary while studying in class. It is already known that lack of vocabulary knowledge is the biggest barrier for foreign language learners. So, if they have known learning vocabulary strategies, they can tackle their reading passage and use it properly in productive skills, speaking and writing. Learning vocabulary has been troublesome for most of the foreign language learners. In accordance with Md. Alul Alam, Wilkins (1972) stated that "There is not much value in being able to produce grammatical sentences if one had not got the vocabulary that is needed to convey what one wishes to say ... While without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed" (p97).

Vocabulary definition

Definition of vocabulary is identified "words must know to communicate effectively; words in speaking (expressive vocabulary) and words in listening (receptive vocabulary)" (Neuman&Dwyer, 2009, p.385). According to Mofareh Alqahtani cited in Ur (1998) is that "Vocabulary can be defined, roughly, as the words we teach in the foreign language. However, a new item of vocabulary may be more

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the vocabulary features and learning strategies for language learners. Through using wide range of vocabulary and effective strategies, learners are able to develop their vocabulary. Since the vocabulary knowledge is vital for all four language skills, listening, reading, speaking and writing, it is necessary to determine how they can tackle the text which they have never encountered. To be able to know and cope with a wide range of vocabulary, it is needed for learners to know effective strategies for learning vocabulary.

KEYWORDS: *vocabulary, strategies*

INTRODUCTION

English has been widely used around the world. Even though other languages are getting popular today, more and more learners who study English are increasing up until now. The role of English has become more and more prominent in every sector compared to the past in accordance with the changes on economy, education standard, and technology together with the development of international relationship. Apparently, English has become in great demand in every society, especially for international relations, to express ideas, to share skills, knowledge and experience, and to exchange information. Above these reasons, to use it proficiently is chiefly rely on to know and use of the vocabulary of target language.

than just a single word: for example, post office, and mother-in-law, which are made up of two or three words but express a single idea."

Therefore, learning vocabulary is the most effective for learners to study the foreign language. Having adequate vocabulary, learners can produce the target language in productive skills if they input it from listening and reading; receptive skills.

Classification of vocabulary learning strategies

Vocabulary learning strategies are thought to be a subordinate element of language use strategies and language learning. Some useful systems include four strategies groups: Social Strategies (SOC), Memory Strategies (MEM), Cognitive Strategies (COG), and Metacognitive Strategies (MET). With Social Strategies, learners interact with each other to develop language learning. Memory Strategies (MEM) is used the approaches which relate new material through with existing knowledge before. Cognitive Strategies (COG) show the common function of manipulation or transformation of the target language. Metacognitive Strategies (MET) consist of a conscious overview of the learning process and making decisions about planning, monitoring, or evaluating the best way to study. In cataloging strategies, Oxford's classification method was thought to be insufficient. Having insufficient Oxford's taxonomy, "category in Oxford's taxonomy which adequately describe the kind of strategies used by an individual when faced with discovering a new word's meaning without resource to another person's expertise" (Schmitt, 1997, p. 205) a new one for the strategies, determination strategies (DET) was created. There are altogether ten strategies.

Determination strategies

There are some ways such as finding meaning finding guessing meaning from the language structure, guessing from an L1 cognate, guessing from context, using reference materials, or asking someone. From these four choices, these strategies assist getting knowledge of a new word. The new word's part of speech, which enable for learners in guessing process, may be noticed by the learners. "Cognates are words in different languages which have descended from a common parent word." (Schmitt1997) It is easier to guess and remember new words if the L2 words correlate with mother tongue of the learners. In spoken communication, meaning can be predicted through gesture or intonation. In reading activity, the meaning of the word can be deduced from the surrounding words in the text. Another way of finding the meaning of the words is by using reference materials; dictionary.

Social Strategies

A method to find a new meaning uses social strategy of asking someone, especially teacher, who knows. When teachers are asked for help, they give various way such as, giving L1 translation, synonym, paraphrasing the definition, and so forth. The best and easy way for learners is L1 translation. However, there may be some erroneous meaning because there may be no exact definition with L1. It is also necessary for learners to know collocational, stylistic and syntactic differences.

Memory Strategies

Memory is obviously essential to all learning and so prominently in second language learning. And memory relates to any language learning.

"Research in memory suggests that words are stored and remembered in a network of associations. These associations can be of many types and be linked in a number of ways. Words in our mental lexicon, for example, are tied to each other not only by meaning, form and sound, but also by sight." (Nattinger 1998) It is important to hold the span of memory. Many memorizing systems depend on the principles of association and imagination. Rote learning (or learning by heart) is known to be the best. Mnemonics is associated with known word, imagery form, or grouping. Many kinds of previous known words combine with a new word.

Imagery

By studying new words with pictures of the meaning is more useful than studying its definitions. Linking target language words with image has seemed better than linking with their mother tongue. On the other hand, learners are able to innovate the meaning of word with their own mental pictures. Reading the paragraph repeatedly is not as effective as mental imagination. A new word is related to learner's personal experience of the concept.

Related words

New words can also be connected with the other words of the foreign language the learners have already known. It contains some kind of relationship, such as coordination (rice – other kinds of grains like wheat, rye), synonym, or antonym. Some words are similar in meaning which relate to other words in their set.

Unrelated words

Unlike related words, it is also effective for learners to be able to connect the words which is no relation with the word each other. Peg or hook words is a kind of unrelated word. First, learners have to memorise a rhyme like 'one is bun, two is shoe, etc.' Then, imagination picture is set up for the word to be remembered and the peg word.

Grouping

To get assist for learners to recall the vocabulary, a crucial way is grouping. Learners are able to collect the words into group. When learners are given lists of some vocabulary, they can recall the words randomly, which are belonging to each meaning. To improve recall, it is important for learners to catagorise the same -word group. However, it is more convenient for learners who are more proficient in language. List of words in single column is not as good as list of words in diagonal. The target words can be collected together in a story or in sentences naturally or used in sentences.

Word's orthographical or phonological form

In order to make easy to recall, concentrating on the target word's orthographical or phonological form is taken into account. The spelling or pronunciation of a word can explicitly be studied. It is easier to remember that orthographical form of a word is visualized and another one is to make a mental representation of the sound of a word. Whatever the shape of word it is, the most prominent feature is the initial letter of the word. The most prominent features for the learners is underlining the first letter or outlining the words with lines.

The most scrutinized mnemonic strategy may be a method combining the phonological forms and meaning of mother tongue and foreign language. Learners require using the Keyword Method in which learners have to find a L1 word which resembles the target L2 word. Then it is needed to form an image integrating the two concepts. The Keyword Method is highly effective in upgrading the recall of words.

Other memory strategies

Analysing the word structure is also useful for determining meaning of words and its affixes, root and word class which is an effective for integrating its meaning. Through paraphrasing, learners will be taught the word meaning. In accordance with the manipulation effort consisting of reformulating the word's meaning, this is a memory strategy improving recall of a word. To upgrade the vocabulary skills, analyzing and learning the individual words of multi-word chunks and using it is a helpful way. To be easy to recall the word, using physical action while learning is an effective one.

Cognitive strategies

This strategy is not concentrated on manipulative mental processing, although it is the same as memory strategies. This involves studying vocabulary using with mechanical means and use it repeatedly. Successively write and say a word repeat again and again is the most common around the world. These strategies are used by many learners who have high levels of proficiency. Using flash cards and word lists is the initial exposure to a word. Using aids is another kind of this strategy. It encourages learners to invent their own style for newly learned words by taking notes in class.

Metacognitive strategies

By having an overview of the learning process generally, learners use this strategy to manage and assess their learning. The more exposure the learners get, the more proficiency they have. So, learners need to expand the exposure of the target language. Interacting with the native speakers can upgrade the input level of the language because it is employed as a controlling of language learning. Learners must make specific schedule to practice the target language. It is more effective than random. Since native speakers know portion of the large number of words, foreign language learners bear into mind that they cannot learn all of the words.

Conclusion

Above are the collections of conventional vocabulary learning strategies. Vocabulary, through which learners can convey their ideas and information, is needed for learners to enhance. If the learners have the enough vocabulary knowledge, they will be able to cope with the barriers they faced in studying and practicing their four skills. Today, 21st century, there will be some more strategies for learning vocabulary depending on the advanced technology. This is another aspect for me to do research in compared with conventional strategies. To increase the vocabulary knowledge is thought considered to be the aim of the learners. It is believed that they can have an unique strategy based on the conventional one.

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